

About the Impact of Audio Quality on Overall Listening Experience

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ABSTRACT

When listening to music, rating the overall listening experience takes many different aspects into account, e. g. the provided audio quality, the listener's mood, the song that is played back etc. Music that is distributed over the Internet is usually encoded into a compressed audio format. Compressed audio formats are evaluated by expert listeners who rate these audio formats according to the perceived audio quality. Much effort is put into researching techniques for encoding music by having better audio quality at lower bit rates. Nevertheless, the beneficial effect that the audio quality has on the overall listening experience is not fully known.

This paper presents the results of an experiment that was carried out to examine the influence that a song and audio quality have on the overall listening experience. The 27 participants rated their personal overall listening experience of music items which were played back in different levels of audio quality.

Since listeners have different preferences when rating overall listening experience, the participants were divided into two groups of listeners according to their responses: song likers and audio quality likers. For both types of listeners, the effect of the audio quality on the rating of overall listening experience is shown.

1. INTRODUCTION

When we listen to music, it is probably not only the music itself which makes us like it or not. For a rating of the overall listening experience, we probably put emotional aspects into account which e. g. could be an individual experience we made in our life that we are connecting to the song [1]. The influence of such emotional aspects and their impact on the overall listening experience differs from person to person and research is far away from fully understanding the effects of emotions in music [2]. Besides emotion-related aspects, the provided audio quality probably influences the overall listening experience as well. This influence of audio quality becomes apparent when we listen to broadcast radio, and the reception is getting so poor that we turn off the radio or switch to another channel.

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In the context of digital distribution, music is provided in uncompressed or compressed formats. Since the upcoming of MP3, compressed formats have become more popular and are nowadays used by most of the Internet music providers. In the last decades, a lot of research effort has been put into improving the audio quality of compressed music. For the evaluation of compressed formats, MUSHRA [3] or BS.1116-1 [4] are often used where the rating is done by so-called expert listeners trained to focus on audio quality related differences between a given reference and the compressed audio signal while suppressing emotional influences. Since the audio quality rated according to MUSHRA or BS.1116-1 does not fully correlate with overall listening experience, the question arises: What is the impact of higher audio quality on the overall listening experience?

2. RELATED WORK

In 2005, James L. Barbour published a study for answering the question whether normal listeners are able to identify any significant differences between multichannel audio codecs [5]. He came to the conclusion that normal consumers listening to commercial releases on good quality audio equipment at home are able to perceive differences between some uncompressed and compressed digital audio delivery formats, depending of the style of music, the production values of the surround mix and the data rate.

In 2005, Francis Rumsey *et al.* presented the results of two experiments with the purpose to find out what relationships between experienced listener ratings of multichannel audio quality and naïve listener preferences exist [6]. They stated that there is a relatively large similarity between the basic audio quality scores acquired from the experienced listeners and preference scores elicited from the naïve listeners.

Blauert and Jekosch structured the broad field of sound quality evaluation into a four-layer model [7]. They defined Aural-communication Quality as the most abstract layer containing the so-called product-sound quality which is the quality from an user's point of view.

In this paper the term overall listening experience covers all aspects which are taken into account by listeners when rating music. Therefore, the term overall listening experience as it is used in this paper is related to Quality of Experience (QoE). An overview about Quality of Experience models is given by Laghari and Connelly [8].

Figure 1. Block diagram of the stimuli manipulation.

3. EXPERIMENT

3.1 Stimuli

Six music excerpts having nine different audio quality levels served as stimuli. The audio quality levels were obtained by limiting the bandwidth and distorting the music excerpt in the frequency domain. The cut-off frequencies used for limiting the bandwidth were 920 Hz, 3150 Hz and 15500 Hz. Distortion was introduced by quantizing the magnitudes of the spectral coefficients in 8, 16 and 4096 quantization levels. The purpose of the different audio quality levels was to add artifacts which are common when encoding music into compressed audio formats. An overview of the processing applied to the stimuli is depicted in Figure 1.

The challenge in the music excerpt selection was to find excerpts that have an emotional influence on the participants, while each audio quality level should result in approximately the same perceived audio quality for all music excerpts.

For having a strong emotional influence on the participant, the song and its level of awareness of the music excerpt were decided to be important. Therefore 79 music excerpts of ten seconds duration were chosen from a large database such that a recognizable part of the song (e. g. refrain) was selected. Moreover, the song had to be ranked in known record charts which was expected to represent the level of awareness. In the second selection step, the spectral flatness and spectral centroid of the 79 music excerpts were computed.

The spectral flatness was used as a simple feature for roughly representing the perceived effect of distortion in the frequency domain:

$$\text{spectral flatness} = \frac{\sqrt[N]{\prod_{n=0}^{N-1} X(n)}}{\frac{\sum_{n=0}^{N-1} X(n)}{N}}, \quad (1)$$

where $X(n)$ is the magnitude of bin number n and N is

Song	Interpret	Flatness	Centroid[Hz]
Feel	Robbie Williams	0.289	3736
Hold on me	Marlon Roudette	0.299	3636
Love Today	Mika	0.308	3887
Paid my Dues	Anastacia	0.317	3556
Summertime	Kenny Chesney	0.306	3658
Respect Yourself	Joe Cocker	0.343	3595

Table 1. Selected music excerpts and their spectral flatness and spectral centroid.

the total number of bins.

The spectral centroid was used as a representing feature for limiting the bandwidth:

$$\text{spectral centroid} = \frac{\sum_{n=0}^{N-1} f(n) X(n)}{\sum_{n=0}^{N-1} X(n)}, \quad (2)$$

where $X(n)$ is the magnitude of bin number n , $f(n)$ is the center frequency of bin number n and N is the total number of bins.

A cluster of 20 music excerpts represented by their spectral flatness and spectral centroid was computed, where the sum of the Euclidean distances between all nodes was minimal. In a final step, the selected 20 music excerpts were manually reduced to 6 excerpts according to their expected emotional influence on the overall listening experience. Table 1 shows the final selection of music excerpts including their spectral flatness and spectral centroid.

The selected music excerpts were down-mixed from stereo to mono and their loudness was normalized according to EBU R128 recommendation [9].

The low-pass filter for limiting the bandwidth was realized by two biquad filters in series. The cut-off frequencies (920 Hz, 3150 Hz and 15500 Hz) for limiting the bandwidth correspond to the cut-off frequencies of the 8th, 16th and 24th critical band of the Bark scale [10].

To introduce distortion, the magnitudes of spectral coefficients obtained from short-time Fourier Transform (STFT) were quantized. The boundaries for the quantization intervals were calculated as follows:

$$Q_{\text{Bound}}(i) = 1.0 - \sqrt{\frac{\log(N-i)}{\log N}}, \quad (3)$$

where i is the boundary index and N the number of total boundaries. The corresponding quantization value for each interval is calculated as follows:

$$Q_{\text{Value}}(i) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } i = 0 \\ \frac{Q_{\text{Bound}}(i) + Q_{\text{Bound}}(i+1)}{2} & \text{if } i > 0 \end{cases}, \quad (4)$$

where i is the interval index. Input values are mapped to quantization values according to

$$Q(x) = Q_{\text{Value}}(i), \quad (5)$$

when $Q_{\text{Bound}}(i) \leq Q(x)$ and $Q_{\text{Bound}}(i+1) > Q(x)$. The details of the distortion processing including frequency domain transformation are depicted as a block diagram in Figure 2. For the STFT, a square-root Hann window with

Figure 2. Block diagram of quantization.

a size of 512 samples and an overlap size of 256 samples was used. Before quantization, the values were normalized from 0 to 1 by using the maximum value as target value 1.

After processing the distortion, the loudness was again normalized using the EBU R128 recommendation. The last processing step consisted of adding a 500 ms fade-in and fade-out effect to the music excerpts.

3.2 Participants

The experiment was attended by 27 participants including researchers, students and related persons of the International Audio Laboratories Erlangen. 12 participants had a professional background in audio and 18 participants were familiar with listening tests. 25 participants were between 20 and 29 years old and 2 were between 30 and 39 years old. Since especially the participants with a professional background in audio are in touch with audio quality in their everyday work, it was assumed that these participants are more sensitive to audio quality than randomly selected par-

Total	Age group	professionals	listening test
27	25 [20-29]	15 [no]	9 [no]
		10 [yes]	6 [yes]
	2 [30-39]	2 [yes]	10 [yes]
			2 [yes]

Table 2. Information about the participants.

Figure 3. Experiment User Interface.

ticipants with not such background. Detailed information about the participants are described in Table 2.

3.3 Method

The participants were instructed to rate the music excerpts in how much they like it by using a five-star scale. They were told that the music excerpts differ in song and quality. In the instruction, it was also emphasized that it is asked for the listener's personal rating and they should put everything into account what they would do in a real world scenario. This additional instruction note was added since pilot tests showed that some listeners tend to rate only the audio quality no matter what instructions say. The reason for this is that very often the listening experiments conducted at our institute focus on audio quality.

After reading the instructions the participants did a training. This training phase was added to familiarize the participants with the rating scale, range of audio quality levels and songs. During the training phase the participants listened to all six music excerpts, each in lowest quality (bandwidth = 920 Hz and distortion = 8 quantization levels) and highest quality (bandwidth = 15500 Hz and distortion = 4096 quantization levels), making 24 items in total. Pilot tests showed that adding this training phase leads to more reliable responses but as a consequence listeners tend to become more audio quality aware. For the training, the same experiment question and scale were used as for the actual listening test which started right after the training.

Then, the participants listened to 54 items (6 music excerpts · 3 bandwidth levels · 3 distortion levels). The experiment question was formulated as follows: "How do you like this music item?". Participants were allowed to play back an item as often as they wanted. The participants rated the items by using a five-star Likert scale. The stars were labeled with "Very Bad", "Bad", "Average", "Good" and "Very Good". The user interface is shown in Figure 3.

At last, the participants were asked how much was their

Figure 4. Distribution of all 162 *Reference Ratings* (6 items · 27 participants).

Variable	Kendall's Tau	p-Value
Bandwidth	0.552	0
Distortion	0.142	2.908e-10
Reference Rating	0.269	0

Table 3. Correlation between *Overall Listening Experience* and *Bandwidth*, *Distortion* and *Reference Rating*.

overall listening experience rating influenced by the audio quality and the song. The responses were given by a Likert scale with the values “Strongly Agree”, “Agree”, “Neutral”, “Disagree” and “Strongly Disagree”.

The experiment was done using open electrostatic Stax SR-507 headphones with SRM-600 driver unit. The system was calibrated to 75 dBA SPL for a 1000 Hz sine. Completing the listening test took each participant about 15 minutes. As mentioned before, the music excerpts were normalized according to EBU R128 which recommends to normalize at -23 dB.

4. RESULTS

The main hypothesis is formulated as whether bandwidth and distortion correlates with rating of overall listening experience. *Overall Listening Experience* is the dependent variable and *Bandwidth* (representing cut-off frequency) and *Distortion* (representing quantization levels) are the independent variables. Another variable, *Reference Rating*, is calculated from *Overall Listening Experience* for the statistical analysis. *Reference Rating* is the response of *Overall Listening Experience* that was given when *Bandwidth* is 15500 Hz and *Distortion* has 4096 quantization levels. Distribution of reference ratings are depicted as histogram in Figure 4.

Table 3 shows the results of correlations with *Overall Listening Experience* by using Kendall's Tau (0 = no correlation, 1 = perfect correlation) which is a ranked correlation coefficient. The correlation and all following calculations are calculated without the data which was used for *Reference Rating*, since this data is used as independent variable and e. g. including would lead to higher correlation values.

Correlation with bandwidth is very strong (= 0.552) which

Figure 5. Kendall's Tau correlation between *Overall Listening Experience* and *Reference Rating* and its p-value for each participant. All participants having a correlation coefficient greater than 0.25 are marked as song likers.

is expected since very low levels of bandwidth were used. The very weak correlation between *Overall Listening Experience* and *Distortion* (= 0.142) is a bit surprising, as the first two levels of distortion were very low, too. *Reference Rating* which probably contains some information about participant's emotional value for a music excerpt has a medium correlation (= 0.269).

An individual calculation of Kendall's Tau Correlation between *Overall Listening Experience* and *Reference Rating* for each participant points out that participants have different preferences in rating overall listening experience. Figure 5 shows Kendall's Tau correlation between *Overall Listening Experience* and *Reference Rating* to their p-values for each participant. The results show that a group of participants had at least a medium correlation to *Reference Rating* (≥ 0.25) while their p-values are below a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$. These participants are considered to be more influenced by the song that is played back than the other participants who have weaker correlations.

For further analysis all participants who have a Kendall's Tau coefficient greater than 0.25 are assigned to the song likers group. The remaining participants are assigned to audio quality likers. To avoid confusion, participants who are in the song likers group could also have a strong correlation between their rating and an audio quality variable. In addition, the spread of correlation coefficients shows that the correlation with the song is rather a continuum. The main reason for defining only two groups is that a more detailed distinction would require a larger amount of participants to avoid under-representation.

When correlation values are calculated separately for song likers and audio quality likers, the emotional influence becomes more obvious. For the song likers, *Reference Rating* correlates nearly the same as *Bandwidth* to *Overall Listening Rating*. Due to the high p-value, no reliable statement can be made for *Distortion*. Correlation values for audio quality likers and song likers are shown in Table 4 and 5.

In Figure 6, the ratio between *Overall Listening Experi-*

Variable	Kendall's Tau	p-Value
Bandwidth	0.530	0
Distortion	0.018	0.516
Reference Rating	0.192	6.961e-13

Table 4. Correlation between *Overall Listening Experience* and *Bandwidth*, *Distortion* and *Reference Rating* of audio quality likers.

Variable	Kendall's Tau	p-Value
Bandwidth	0.430	0
Distortion	0.002	0.972
Reference Rating	0.405	8.882e-16

Table 5. Correlation between *Overall Listening Experience* and *Bandwidth*, *Distortion* and *Reference Rating* of song likers listeners.

ence and *Reference Rating* for each *Bandwidth* is shown. A ratio value of 1 would mean that *Overall Listening Experience* for the particular *Bandwidth* level is the same as for *Bandwidth* = 15500 Hz and a ratio of 1.5 would mean the rating was 50% higher. One can see that audio quality likers have lower values than song likers. This means that audio quality likers are more critical in their rating when audio quality is decreased. Besides that, the ratio values of audio quality likers decrease more for each bandwidth limitation level than for song likers.

A cumulative link model of *Overall Listening Experience* was calculated (Table 6). As the previous analysis indicated, *Bandwidth* had more influence on *Overall Listening Experience* than *Distortion*. Furthermore, song likers gave slightly higher ratings.

At the end of the experiment the participants were asked how much their rating was influenced by song and audio quality. It was expected that song likers do much more strongly agree that their rating was influenced by the song compared to audio quality likers. As Figure 7 shows such a trend could not be confirmed. Figure 8 shows that for both types of listeners audio quality is important for their rating.

5. DISCUSSION

The presented results indicate that all ratings were strongly correlated with bandwidth. Interesting is the fact that the mean of *Overall Listening Experience* to *Reference Rating* ratio for song likers had a value of 0.75 (0.67 for audio quality likers) for *Bandwidth* of 3150 Hz. Such a bandwidth degradation is considered as a strong impairment and a much lower ratio was expected. Some participants who rated lower bandwidths the same or higher than reference bandwidth stated that lower bandwidths reminds them of festivals or concerts resulting in a positive effect on their rating.

We assume that especially the song likers would rate lower bandwidths in a real world scenario much higher than in this experiment. Many participants reported that they got annoyed by listening to the same songs repeatedly which made them focus on audio quality. Since this reaction was

Figure 6. *Overall Listening Rating* to *Reference Rating* ratio for all three bandwidths. Only samples with *Distortion* of 4096 levels are included.

Coefficient	Estimate	Std. Error	z-value	p-value
Bandwidth = 3150	2.0788	0.1433	14.505	<2e-16
Bandwidth = 15500	3.9807	0.1840	21.632	<2e-16
Distortion = 16	0.7560	0.1294	5.842	5.17e-09
Distortion = 4096	1.0305	0.1554	6.632	3.32e-11
Reference Rating = 2	3.4240	1.0729	3.191	0.00142
Reference Rating = 3	4.8280	1.0697	4.513	6.38e-06
Reference Rating = 4	5.7951	1.0712	5.410	6.31e-08
Reference Rating = 5	5.7654	1.0797	5.340	9.32e-08
Liker Type = song	0.2750	0.1386	1.984	0.04728
Threshold coefficients:				
	Estimate	Std. Error	z-value	
very bad bad	6.685	1.082	6.178	
bad average	8.596	1.093	7.867	
average good	10.550	1.103	9.563	
good very good	12.953	1.128	11.480	
Residual Deviance: 2704.485				
AIC: 2730.485				

Table 6. Cumulative Link Model of *Overall Listening Experience*.

expected, we integrated the very long training phase where participants listened to each song twice (best quality and worst quality). Therefore, we assumed that at the beginning of the actual experiment the participants were more influenced by audio quality than they would be without the training phase. This was also reported by several song likers that their sensitivity to audio quality increased due to the training phase. Since in a real world scenario, listeners have no reference what the music they are listening to sounds in best quality, their ratings would not be as critical as in this experiment.

Some participants reported about the distortion that it felt like being masked by the bandwidth limitation which is also seen in the statistical analysis results where distortion correlates very weakly with *Overall Listening Experience*. It should not be concluded from the results that bandwidth is more important than distortion for *Overall Listening Experience* since only three levels of each variable were examined. Moreover, music can be distorted in frequency domain in various ways, other algorithms for distortion might lead to other results. It was also reported that it is harder to remember the best quality reference of distortion than it is for bandwidth. It can be assumed that for non-expert

Figure 7. Distribution of participants’ responses of how much their rating was influenced by the song.

Figure 8. Distribution of participants’ responses of how much their rating was influenced by audio quality.

listeners building a short-time reference for bandwidth is easier than for frequency domain distortion.

In our statistical analysis, *Reference Rating* was used as some sort of dependent variable like *Bandwidth* and *Distortion*. This means when the selection of music excerpts matches a participant’s taste of music, *Reference Rating* has higher values in average than if the selection would not match his taste of music. This results in an unequally distributed data of *Overall Listening Experience* for *Reference Rating*. To overcome, one would need to ask each participant before the test for five songs which would be rated from one to five stars and use them as stimuli. But then each participant would listen to different songs where limiting the bandwidth or distortion would result in different perceived audio quality artifacts. That is why we carefully selected six music excerpts from a large database where differences of the perceived artifacts were within reasonable limits.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The results of the experiment show that rating music in overall listening experience is strongly influenced by bandwidth when the listeners is presented a reference of the music in maximum available bandwidth. In this experiment, the participants were familiarized with the minimum and maximum available bandwidth by a training phase.

The participants were divided into two types of listeners by using the correlation between reference rating and overall listening experience: audio quality likers and song likers. Audio quality likers have stronger correlation with bandwidth and their rating was more critical than song likers’ rating.

Further research will look into the effect of bandwidth limitation on overall listening experience in more detail.

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